

GREEN JOBS – WHAT DIGITALIZATION AND THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT HAVE BROUGHT TO LABOUR

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Abstract

In a constantly changing world, where the economy, the environment, and labour are increasingly intertwined, the question arises: can new forms of work contribute to a more sustainable future? Green jobs, as a concept of the modern paradigm, have the potential to change the structure of the labour market while at the same time being in the "service" of nature and the environment.

Analysing contemporary labour trends, driven by digitalization, new legal regulations, and collective ecological awakening, the authors of this paper also raise the issue of the impact of technological progress, normative development, and socio-economic opportunities, focusing on the relationship between digitalization and sustainability. The concept of sustainable development, especially in the area of labour, represents a kind of ethical revolution in the way things have been done so far, which places sustainability as a value, not just as a strategy. Additionally, within the framework of their analysis, the authors also address the aspect of workers' skills and qualifications and the need for further education in order to transition to green jobs, emphasizing the importance of educational programs and professional development.

By identifying the advantages and challenges of new "green" sectors, the foundation is being laid for effectively adapting the workforce to the demands of future, sustainable economies. But what remains most challenging is inequality, and will this shift deepen existing gaps or be an opportunity to overcome them?

Keywords: jobs, green transformation, sustainable development, digitalization

INTRODUCTION

Vivimus in tempore transitus — We live in a time of transition. Our world, built on the principles of industrial progress of the last century, is increasingly facing the limits of its ecological, social and economic sustainability. Work is becoming a central field of transformation, the digital revolution accompanied by environmental risks necessitates a complete change of the system on which employment relations, productivity and the basic concepts of work are based – as times change, we must change too.

Green jobs are a reflection of the new relationships between labour, nature, and technology, that is, the idea that jobs must be in harmony with nature. In this abyss between tradition and transformation, a fundamental question arises: Can labour—what defines us as a society—become a tool for maintaining, rather than destroying, the world around us?

The European Green Deal is an extremely ambitious plan for the old continent to transition to a more sustainable economy. The Union aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, requiring significant changes in industries, especially in the energy and transport sectors, agriculture, and manufacturing, in the member states, but also in the candidate countries. The creation of more fully or partially green jobs is of crucial importance, especially in the mentioned sectors, because through them not only do companies align themselves with environmental goals, but they also create the potential to create millions of new employment opportunities, which should serve as a balance for the large number of projected job losses as a result of the obligations of the agreement itself that are binding on the signatory countries. Traditionally industrial countries that operate in mining, coal and oil extraction, and other heavy industries will be most affected by these processes, given that in those countries these industries have the largest share of GDP and are the largest employers, which means that millions of people are directly affected by these changes.

The transition to sustainability involves significant restructuring of the companies themselves, changes in production processes, more rigorous rules that must be respected, and large financial expenditures that will be borne by employers. It is no longer enough to be a classic “worker”, but workers must keep up with the new digital reality. However, digitalization is a kind of paradox: while some jobs die, new ones are born, but they require other, different skills, and this creates inequality.

Digitalization, on the one hand, appears to be an ambivalent phenomenon: it offers great potential for optimization, efficiency, automation of processes, and increased productivity, but at the same time, it replaces certain traditional forms of work. However, digitalization should be analysed in terms of creating new systems that will help repair the environmental damage caused by traditional industries and promote green growth. It is in this combination of technology and ethics that the concept of green jobs is born, which overcomes the dichotomy between economic development and environmental protection.

This paper analyses precisely this intersection between digitalization and sustainable development as driving forces in shaping the new world of work. It will explore how new technologies can contribute to the creation of green jobs, as well as the ethical, economic, and social implications of that process.

The impact of digitalization in creating green jobs

Digitalization is a process that began long ago, with the so-called Fourth Industrial Revolution, which is moving towards the Fifth Industrial Revolution (**Schwab, n.d.**). Digitalization is a complex process that refers to the integration of digital technologies into all areas of business and society, resulting in significant changes in how industries function, how people work, and how economic value is created. In recent years, digitalization has become one of the most influential drivers of change in the European Union (EU) labour market, transforming sectors, jobs, and the skills needed. The world of work as we once knew it is no more.

Digitalization has had a significant impact on jobs globally, but also within the European Union, and even at the national level. This was especially evident during the

coronavirus pandemic, where we have witnessed certain shifts in some job categories, creating a need for new jobs and workers who have the ability to adapt quickly to changes in labour.

The introduction of advanced digital technologies—such as automation, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, the Internet of Things (IoT), and cloud computing—has revolutionized industries across the EU. The impact of digitalization can be seen in almost every sector, from manufacturing and agriculture to finance and healthcare. However, the effects are not uniform, and the extent to which digitalization transforms jobs depends on a number of factors, including the sector's reliance on technology, the availability of digital infrastructure, and the pace at which companies adopt new digital solutions.

The benefits of digitalization can be seen most clearly through the automation of repetitive tasks and processes in sectors such as manufacturing and logistics, which are now performed with digital solutions or robotic tools, resulting in increased productivity and reduced costs. Robotics is increasingly common in the automotive industry, where machines now perform tasks that were previously performed by humans, for example. Drones are more and more used for deliveries, while artificial intelligence algorithms are being applied in logistics. In this constellation, there seems to be less demand for people in traditional job positions, such as truck drivers, warehouse workers, and conveyor belt operators, as many manual tasks are replaced by robots and algorithms.

But what does this actually mean?

As we have mentioned, digitalization is not only leading to job losses but also creating new opportunities in areas such as data analytics, cybersecurity, software development, and digital marketing. As businesses embrace digital technologies, there is an increasing demand for highly skilled workers who can design, implement, and manage these technologies. The shift to more digitally oriented business models has led to entirely new professions, with these jobs offering competitive salaries and career advancement opportunities.

However, one of the biggest challenges that digitalization brings is precisely the loss of jobs that inevitably cease to be needed. The automation of tasks that were once performed by people—whether in factories, service centres, or administration—can lead to a significant reduction in demand for certain categories of jobs. According to a 2020 report by the European Commission, automation could lead to the displacement of up to 7 million jobs across the EU by 2030, especially in areas such as manufacturing, retail, and transport (**European Commission, 2020**).

At the same time, digitalization has increased the demand for higher levels of skills and education. For example, as industries become more reliant on digital tools, there is an increasing demand for workers skilled in areas such as coding, software engineering, machine learning, and data analytics. These jobs are often associated with higher salaries and better long-term prospects compared to traditional professions, but the skills gap between workers in the digital economy and those in more traditional sectors poses a significant challenge.

A key aspect of digitalization is the shift towards “knowledge-based” jobs, which require workers to have strong analytical and digital skills and problem-solving abilities.

Digitalization has also led to the emergence of hybrid job categories that combine traditional skills with digital ones. These “digitally enhanced” jobs include positions such as digital project managers and marketing automation specialists. For example, in

marketing, the increased use of AI and machine learning tools has led to a rise in jobs focused on analysing consumer behaviour through data insights, rather than relying on traditional marketing strategies.

Digitalization has also led to new forms of work, such as remote work, freelance work, and work on digital platforms. This shift towards more flexible, decentralized work arrangements has led to the rise of platforms such as Uber, Airbnb, and Upwork, which allow individuals to offer services remotely or on a part-time basis. New technologies such as digital platforms designed to connect users with each other and with advertisers, on which social networks are built, provide additional support for the spread of the “stall economy” (Ristovski, 2024). While this has provided greater flexibility and opportunities for some workers, it has also raised concerns about job security, benefits, and the erosion of traditional labour protections. The work of the platform has highlighted the most important challenges, including low and irregular wages, job insecurity, issues related to algorithmic control and surveillance, data protection issues, lack of rights and protections from employment, and limited collective representation (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2024). However, in addition to the positive type of freedom of association and action, there is also a negative type that manifests itself in the right of an employee not to be a member of a union without employment law consequences, i.e., the freedom not to be a member of a union at all, as well as the freedom to leave a union (Jovevski, 2022).

Moreover, digitalization requires not only technical skills but also a range of “soft” skills, including problem-solving, adaptability, and collaboration. As industries embrace automation and artificial intelligence, the ability to work alongside machines, interpret data, and manage complex digital systems is becoming increasingly important. Upskilling and reskilling initiatives are therefore crucial to ensure that workers can transition to new jobs that will require digital competencies.

While it brings significant changes in terms of the elimination of certain categories of jobs and the creation of new ones, it also raises important questions about how workers can adapt to these changes. The transition to a digital economy requires a joint effort from policymakers, businesses, and educational institutions to invest in the upskilling and retraining of the workforce. Thus, the regulation of platform work has become one of the most important issues in order to preserve the European social model in the context of increased digitalization. The EU Directive on improving working conditions in platform work (COM/2021/762) represents the first attempt by the EU to regulate platform work and is part of the EU reform package aimed at regulating the digital economy, which also includes the Digital Markets Act, the Digital Services Act, and the Artificial Intelligence Act (Bertolin, 2024). The directive addresses many of the challenges affecting platform workers in the EU by introducing regulations in several areas: employment status, algorithmic governance, transparency and enforcement, and collective bargaining (Bertolin, 2024).

As digitalization continues to transform the EU labour market, a key challenge will be to ensure that the benefits of these changes are felt equally by all. While some sectors will undoubtedly experience job losses, others will see significant growth in new jobs. By addressing the skills gap, providing support for affected workers, and fostering a culture of continuous learning, we can harness the transformative power of digitalization to create a more dynamic, resilient, and inclusive labour market.

The concept of sustainable development and jobs

One of the main objectives of the European Green Deal is the promotion of green jobs, especially in sectors with high negative environmental impacts. Traditional production processes have proven to be highly polluting (e.g., steel, pulp and paper, and chemical industries), while on the other hand, some of the new high-diffusion technologies have also been shown to have a high environmental impact, for example, agricultural pesticides, solvents, plastics, and fossil fuels (EU-ILO, 2019). This is why areas for new job creation include renewable energy sources, sustainable agriculture, and the circular economy.

In Europe, the transition to wind, solar, and hydropower is expected to generate significant employment opportunities. The European Commission estimates that by 2050, renewable energy could create up to 2 million jobs, particularly in these areas. The new jobs will range from research and development to installation and maintenance.

Sustainable agriculture is another key area where green jobs are expected to grow. The EU's "farm to fork" strategy (European Commission, 2020), a central component of the Green Deal, aims to make food systems healthier and more environmentally friendly. This includes promoting organic farming, reducing pesticide use, enhancing biodiversity, and encouraging local food production. Employment opportunities are expected to grow in areas such as organic farming, agroecology, and sustainable forestry.

The transition to a circular economy, focused on reducing waste and maximizing the reuse, repair, and recycling of materials, is another key component of the Green Deal. The European Commission has highlighted the potential for the circular economy to generate significant employment, particularly in sectors such as recycling, waste management, and product processing.

A report by the European Environment Agency (EEA) estimates that up to 700,000 jobs could be created in the EU by 2030 as a result of the circular economy (European Environment Agency, 2019). These jobs would primarily be located in the construction, electrical, and textile sectors, where there is an increasing demand for resource-efficient and environmentally friendly production processes.

The shift away from fossil fuels, as one of the commitments under the European Green Deal, will potentially have the greatest impact on the labour market. Europe must reduce its dependence on coal, oil, and natural gas to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, and as a result, millions of jobs in the extractive industry and distribution of fossil fuels are at risk. For workers, the challenges relate to job and income security, working conditions, social protection, and access to their fundamental rights to freedom of association and collective bargaining (International Labour Organization, 2021).

These potential job losses will disproportionately affect regions dependent on coal mining, oil extraction and gas production. For example, coal mining communities in countries such as Poland, Germany and the Czech Republic are particularly affected by the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources.

Investing in reskilling and upskilling programs is essential to ensure that workers can move from high-carbon sectors to green jobs. Programs should focus on the specific skills needed in the new digital age and working with renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable industries. The European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan highlights the need for lifelong learning initiatives, which will be essential for workers in fossil fuel industries who may need to acquire new skills to enter the green economy (European Commission, 2022). Collaboration between governments, employers, and

educational institutions, both public and private, is crucial to make long-term plans that will make the transition smoother and more resilient.

One of the elements of the European Green Deal is the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM), which aims to provide financial support to regions and workers affected by the green transition. The JTM includes the Just Transition Fund, which has been allocated €17.5 billion to help diversify the economies of coal-dependent regions, create new jobs, and invest in reskilling programs.

Countries with high levels of automation in industries such as automotive manufacturing (e.g., Germany) or agriculture (e.g., Spain) will face a greater displacement of workers with lower skills and education. At the same time, there will be a need for a significant shift in skills towards high-tech sectors, which require more complex retraining and upskilling programs. The European Commission has stressed the importance of lifelong learning and continuous training to ensure that workers can adapt to the changing labour market. But while there seems to be a political consensus that the promotion of lifelong learning and vocational training by employers and governments is important for shaping the world of work, upskilling cannot always be the “solution” for workers who have lost or will lose their jobs as a result of the introduction of labour-saving technologies (Konle-Seidl & Danesi, 2022).

In a green economy, the concept of “good jobs” includes not only decent wages and working conditions but also environmental sustainability and well-being. Green jobs also make a positive contribution to broader societal goals for environmental protection. Here, the International Labour Organization has taken the position that green jobs should be seen as a path to achieving both social and environmental justice, with an emphasis on workers’ rights, health and safety, and the promotion of decent work standards.

CONCLUSION

Modern economic and social trends confirm the transformative power of digitalization and the concept of sustainable development in creating new, green jobs. In the context of the green economy, digital technologies enable the optimization of energy systems, better waste control, more efficient use of resources, and monitoring of environmental impact. These benefits lead to the creation of green jobs in sectors such as renewable energy sources, energy efficiency, waste management, eco-engineering, and digital services aimed at sustainable practices.

On the other hand, the concept of sustainable labour development imposes new ethical and social standards. Today's jobs should not only be economically sustainable but also socially just and environmentally acceptable. However, despite the numerous positive aspects, this transformation also brings new challenges. There is a risk of digital inequality, technological unemployment, and inadequate preparation of the workforce for the new conditions. Therefore, a systematic and long-term strategy for human capital development is needed—through educational reforms, investment in digital skills, and continuous retraining (World Economic Forum, 2023). Therefore, educational institutions and employment policies have a key role to play, which should enable systematic retraining and alignment of the labour market with the needs of the green digital economy.

From a macroeconomic perspective, the integration of digital technologies into the green economy contributes to strengthening competitiveness, increasing energy independence, and stimulating innovation. At the microeconomic level, however, organizations that apply the principles of digital sustainability become more agile, more

efficient, and more socially responsible. This symbiosis between technology and sustainability redefines the concept of labour—from a traditional, physical activity to an intellectual and creative one.

Finally, we would like to emphasize that digitalization and the concept of sustainable development are key drivers in the creation of new green jobs. The development of more green jobs will create new employment opportunities, foster economic resilience, and guide society towards a greener and fairer future. To harness this potential, a partnership between the state, academia, the private sector, and civil society is necessary. Only through such a collaborative approach can the digital transition truly contribute to sustainable development, creating labour that is both productive and environmentally responsible.

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